

An Analysis of the Sustenance of a Traversable Wormhole under the Most Optimistic Assumptions

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes the sustenance of a traversable wormhole under the most optimistic assumptions, including the violation of the Null Energy Condition, a finite redshift function, static and symmetric geometry, and the satisfaction of the flare-out condition. This study also examines the Morris-Thorne Metric to understand the behavior of the geometry of a traversable wormhole. We investigate the response of the wormhole to perturbations induced in the geometry.

The analysis demonstrates that the wormhole geometry is highly sensitive to small perturbations. We derive a general relation for perturbation in the throat radius δr_0 in terms of a definite integral, demonstrating that perturbations in the throat radius depend on the cumulative distribution of energy density and, therefore, are non-local. The result further demonstrates a non-local coupling between geometry and stress-energy configuration at the throat.

The definite integral solved for a specific shape function of choice yields the relation, $\delta r_0 = \frac{1}{2}\delta b(r_0)$, which demonstrates that the perturbation in the throat directly influences its geometry. We derive another general relation of $\delta r_0 = \frac{\delta b(r_0)}{1-b'(r_0)}$. In this relation, we analyze how changes in $(1 - b'(r_0))^{-1}$ amplify the perturbation at the throat. These results indicate that maintaining a stabilized geometry requires precise coordination between geometry and stress-energy.

Consequently, even under idealized conditions, sustaining a traversable wormhole appears to be extremely difficult.

Keywords: Traversable wormholes, Morris-Thorne metric, General relativity, Exotic matter, Null energy condition, Wormhole stability, Perturbation theory, Spacetime geometry

I. INTRODUCTION

In four-dimensional spacetime, when two distant regions become connected due to extreme curvature, it creates a tunnel-like structure which, in principle, may provide a shorter path [1] between two vastly distinct regions. This embedded curved geometry in spacetime is referred to as a 'wormhole'.

A wormhole is a mathematically valid solution to Einstein's field equations [1, 2]. Though mathematically consistent, it is still studied as a part of theoretical physics, as numerous constraints question their very existence, making these elegant structures a speculative idea. In this paper, we shall investigate whether a wormhole would sustain if certain optimistic assumptions are made.

Exotic matter, radial tension and stress-energy distribution are regarded as the major obstacles to the physical existence of a wormhole [1, 3]. The objective of this paper is to allow the traversable wormhole to bypass these constraints and then analyze its sustenance.

Previous studies have primarily focused on the geometric requirements for traversability, the violation of classical

energy conditions, and the minimization of exotic matter [1, 3, 4]. Stability under perturbations, however, remains an unresolved issue. Even if a traversable configuration is mathematically constructed, small deviations in geometry or stress-energy may destabilize the throat.

This work extends the Morris-Thorne framework by deriving a perturbation relation for δr_0 . It establishes a non-local coupling between geometry and stress-energy and identifies the amplification of perturbations in throat response. We analyze the sustenance of a traversable wormhole under optimistic assumptions using first-order perturbation theory.

II. WORMHOLE GEOMETRY AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The idea of wormholes goes back to the 20th century. A wormhole is a solution to Einstein's field equations of General Relativity. It was first proposed in 1935 by Albert Einstein and Nathan Rosen [2]. The paper published by **Kip Thorne** and **Michael S. Morris** in 1988 indicates that the violation of the **Null Energy Condition** is a requirement to sustain a traversable wormhole [1]. We shall explore the foundation of wormholes in this section.

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In 1915, Einstein published his **General Theory of Relativity** [5], which describes gravitation not as a force but as a curvature formed in spacetime due to mass and energy [5]. This revolutionary idea allows for the possibility of non-trivial topologies, including the hypothetical structure known as a "Wormhole" (or Einstein–Rosen Bridge). This theory also predicts gravitational time dilation caused by strong gravitational fields [6].

e.g., 1 Consider a test particle with negligible mass in empty space. While the particle itself doesn't curve spacetime, its motion is influenced by nearby massive bodies. In the absence of such bodies, the particles move in a straight line through flat spacetime.

FIG. 1. A 2D illustration showcasing the change in spacetime due to a particle with negligible mass.

e.g., 2 Consider a supermassive black hole with strong gravitational effects. In this case, the curvature of the spacetime fabric would be so deep that the time variation between the time flowing under normal circumstances and near a black hole would be great.

FIG. 2. A 2D schematic showing the curvature formed in spacetime due to the presence of mass.

Wormholes are theorized to act as shortcuts in the spacetime, connecting distant locations or even different time frames, enabling rapid travel between them or even time manipulation if one of the ends experiences the effects of time dilation.

A. Einstein - Rosen Bridges

In 1935, Albert Einstein and Nathan Rosen extended a specific solution of Einstein's field equations known as the Schwarzschild solution, which describes the spacetime geometry surrounding a spherical non-rotating mass [6].

By mathematically mirroring this geometry, Einstein and Rosen theorized a tunnel-like structure connecting two different points in spacetime, later known as a wormhole. This hypothetical structure came to be known as the ER bridge.

However, further research showed that these bridges are non-traversable [7]. They collapse almost instantly due to the intense gravitational force near the throat of wormholes, causing the **throat** to pinch shut before light or matter can pass through - making the bridge purely hypothetical and useless for travel or communication in its raw form.

FIG. 3. A 2D diagram of a traversable wormhole, based on Morris-Thorne Metric with a shape function $b(r)$ a redshift function $\Phi(r)$ which is finite everywhere and the minimum radius at the throat $r = r_0$

Although ER bridges satisfy Einstein's field equations, they do not allow for travel or communication. The instability of ER bridges prompted physicists to search for mechanisms to stabilize the wormhole. One proposed solution involves the presence of exotic matter — hypothetical materials with negative energy density to counteract the collapse.

Though a quantum phenomenon known as the Casimir Effect hints at localized negative energy density between closely spaced conducting plates, the magnitude and scale of this effect are extremely limited, and are regarded as insufficient to sustain a macroscopic traversable wormhole.

B. Kip Thorne And Traversable Wormholes

In 1988, physicist *Kip Thorne*, along with *Michael S. Morris*, proposed the idea of a traversable wormhole - one that could, in theory, remain stable long enough for matter or information to pass through.

Their solution to prevent the collapse of the **wormhole throat** suggested the use of exotic matter — a hypothetical material with negative energy density [1]. Unlike normal matter, which curves spacetime inward (like a valley), this unusual matter forms an outward curvature in the spacetime fabric, counteracting the wormhole's natural tendency to pinch off.

FIG. 4. A 2D schematic to highlight the difference in the curvatures formed in spacetime by ordinary matter and exotic matter.

Thorne's work transformed the concept of wormholes from speculative artifacts into legitimate topics of theoretical physics. However, the existence of exotic matter is still a significant challenge for the sustainability of wormholes.

C. Geometry of the Wormhole

Metrics are mathematical tools that tell us how to measure the interval or distance covered by a particle in 3D space; they even allow us to measure the spacetime interval between two events in 4D space.

1. Minkowski Metric — Flat Spacetime

One such metric, which explains the position of any object in flat spacetime, is the **Minkowski Metric**. This model shows how a spacetime interval is independent of all frames of reference [6]. In Minkowski spacetime, all frames of reference will agree on the total interval in spacetime between the two events. Therefore, this spacetime interval is invariant.

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt^2 + dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 \quad (1)$$

Here, the term ds^2 is the spacetime interval between two infinitesimally close events. The terms dx^2 , dy^2 ,

and dz^2 represent the spatial components of the interval. Since the spacetime interval includes both spatial and temporal contributions, $-c^2 dt^2$ represents the temporal component of the interval, dt denotes the change in the time coordinate, and c is the speed of light used to convert time units into length units.

The minus sign before the temporal component shows the fundamental difference between spatial and temporal directions in spacetime.

2. Schwarzschild Metric — Curved Spacetime

The Schwarzschild metric, or the Schwarzschild solution, is the solution to Einstein's field equations. This model explains the gravitational field outside a spherical mass under the assumption that the mass is static and has no charge [6]. The major difference between the Minkowski metric and the Schwarzschild metric is that the latter describes the spacetime interval between two events due to **curved spacetime**, whereas the former measures it in **flat spacetime**.

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} \right) c^2 dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (2)$$

In this metric, c is the speed of light and G is the universal gravitational constant, where c and G are often taken as 1. They are referred as geometrized units.

Here, the term ds^2 represents the spacetime interval between two infinitesimally close events. The term $- \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} \right) c^2 dt^2$ denotes the temporal component of the metric.

The term $\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} \right)^{-1} dr^2$ is the radial component of the metric, which shows that the curvature in spacetime depends on the mass and distance from the center of the non-rotating object.

The term $d\Omega^2$ represents the angular component of the metric and is equal to $d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2$. This term helps describe the spherical geometry of the curvature.

Though the Schwarzschild Metric describes the geometry of spacetime around a spherical, non-rotating mass, other solutions to Einstein's field equations describe different geometries.

3. Morris-Thorne Metric — Wormhole Geometry

The Morris-Thorne metric, proposed by **Kip Thorne** and **Michael S. Morris** in 1988, describes the geometry of a stabilized, traversable wormhole [1]. It includes the **redshift function** and the **shape function**. The redshift function determines the gravitational redshift and

time dilation. The shape function describes whether the mouths of wormholes flare-out or collapse.

$$ds^2 = -e^{2\Phi(r)} dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{b(r)}{r}} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (3)$$

Here, the term ds^2 describes the infinitesimally small distance between the two events in the spacetime interval.

The term $-e^{2\Phi(r)}$ is the temporal component of the metric that represents the **redshift function**. If $\Phi(r)$ diverges, the throat collapses and the event horizon is formed. Thus, to sustain a traversable wormhole, $\Phi(r)$ must be finite everywhere. The redshift function influences gravitational redshift and time dilation which indirectly affects the tidal forces.

$\Phi'(r) = \frac{d\Phi}{dr}$ represents the radial derivative of the redshift function. It describes how $\Phi(r)$ changes with the change in radial coordinate i.e., distance from the center.

Now, the term $\frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{b(r)}{r}}$ is the radial component that determines the shape of the wormhole in spacetime as it includes its **shape function**. There are certain conditions of the shape function $b(r)$ that determine the spatial geometry of the wormhole and the behavior of the throat. These include: Assuming that $r = r_0$ is the minimum radius at the throat.

- Throat exists when : $b(r_0) = r_0$
- For traversability: $b(r) < r$, $r > r_0$, and $b'(r_0) < 1$.
- The Flare-Out Condition [1, 4]: $\frac{b(r) - b'(r)r}{2[b(r)]^2} > 0$

The term $r^2 d\Omega^2$, the angular component of the metric, describes the spherical geometry of the throat of the wormhole. Here, $d\Omega^2 = d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2$.

When the Morris-Thorne Metric is inserted into Einstein's field equations:

$G_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu}$ [5], the result implies that the matter required for the stability of a traversable wormhole must violate the Null Energy Condition near the throat. The Null Energy Condition [3]: $T_{\mu\nu} k^\mu k^\nu \geq 0$ states that the energy density measured by any null observer is non-negative [1]. However, the Morris-Thorne Metric shows that the throat of a traversable wormhole requires the violation of the Null Energy Condition which signifies the requirement of **exotic matter** for the stability of wormholes.

III. CONSTRAINTS ON SUSTAINING A TRAVERSABLE WORMHOLE

In this section, we shall analyze whether a traversable wormhole would sustain itself even under the most optimistic assumptions. A traversable wormhole can attain

stability if it fulfills certain necessary requirements implied by the geometry of the wormhole, such as — exotic matter being available, the redshift function $\Phi(r)$ being finite everywhere, and if the flare-out condition is being satisfied. We shall assume some of these requirements to assess the sustenance of the wormhole.

A. Optimistic Assumptions

In accordance with the Null Energy Condition, the energy density measured by any null observer must be non-negative. However, when the Morris-Thorne Metric is inserted into Einstein's Field Equation: $G_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu}$, it indicates that the throat requires matter with negative energy density i.e., **exotic matter**. Although, quantum effects like the **Casimir effect** can produce localized regions of negative energy density relative to the vacuum state [8, 9], yet no experiment provides evidence for the production of negative energy density on a large-scale, which can help sustain a macroscopic traversable wormhole.

Thus, our **First Assumption** would be the availability and accessibility of exotic matter that can violate the Null Energy Condition ($T_{\mu\nu} k^\mu k^\nu \geq 0$) [10] Violation of classical energy conditions has also been extensively discussed in the wormhole literature [11, 12].

From the Morris-Thorne Metric, we discovered that the redshift function must never diverge to ensure the traversability of a wormhole.

Thus, our **Second Assumption** is that the redshift function is finite everywhere.

$$\text{Assuming : } \Phi(r) < \infty$$

Third Assumption : We also assume that the geometry of the wormhole is static and symmetric. This assumption makes the analysis of the wormhole easier, as it removes complications such as rotation, time dependence, or asymmetry. The use of static and symmetric geometry for wormhole analyses is also well established in the modern literature and has been generalized in subsequent studies [11].

The Morris-Thorne Metric also suggests that the shape function $b(r)$ must satisfy the flare-out condition, otherwise the throat of the wormhole might collapse.

Thus, our **Fourth Optimistic Assumption** is that the geometry of the wormhole is already stabilized and satisfies the flare-out condition.

$$\text{Assuming } b(r_0) = r_0, b'(r_0) < 1,$$

$$\frac{b(r_0) - b'(r_0)r_0}{2[b(r_0)]^2} > 0$$

Under these optimistic assumptions, we now examine whether the wormhole geometry can remain physically sustainable.

B. Energy Requirement Near The Throat

As discussed in earlier sections, when Einstein's field equations ($G_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu}$) are applied to the Morris-Thorne Metric, the result violates the Null Energy Condition. As derived in [1], the result can be expressed as:

$$\rho + P_r < 0 \quad (4)$$

$$P_r < -\rho$$

after taking : $c = 1$ [geometrized units]

Here, $\rho(r) = \frac{b'(r)}{8\pi r^2}$ is the equation obtained from the Morris-Thorne Metric inserted into Einstein's field equation. The result $P_r < -\rho$ shows that the geometry near the throat requires extreme radial tension. This radial pressure is strongly negative and has a larger magnitude than energy density. Due to the large radial tension (negative radial pressure) τ_r along the radial direction, the configuration of exotic matter near the throat may be physically difficult to maintain. The geometry here may be difficult to maintain under such extreme stress-energy conditions.

Here, τ_r represents the radial tension. It can be expressed as:

$$\tau_r = -P_r \quad (5)$$

The equation above suggests that the magnitude of radial tension should be large enough to exceed the energy density.

Substituting (3) into (2)

$$\rho - \tau_r < 0$$

$$\boxed{\tau_r(r_0) > \rho(r_0), r = r_0} \quad (6)$$

Maintaining such a stress-energy distribution near the throat in these conditions requires a precise distribution of energy. Maintaining such a configuration may be physically difficult under extreme stress-energy conditions.

Therefore, even under the optimistic assumption of granting the availability and accessibility of exotic matter, the stability of exotic matter and the wormhole may not be guaranteed.

C. Sensitivity Of The Wormhole

This section analyzes the sensitivity of the wormhole geometry to external perturbations. In this section, we shall analyze how perturbations in the geometry of the wormhole may lead to consequences in which maintaining the wormhole may be too difficult.

We have provided mathematical frameworks to analyze the results in a more consistent manner. All the calculations involving the use of perturbations and Taylor Expansion are solved up to the first-order terms to ensure linearity in the equations [13]. It is done for analytical tractability.

The next subsections involve the analysis of the changes caused by perturbations in the radial coordinate, the energy density, radial tension, and the shape function. The objective is to discover how sensitive the geometry of the wormhole is to such disturbances and whether it would sustain under our optimistic assumptions.

1. Variation Of Geometry Of The Wormhole Under Perturbations

In this subsection, we shall analyze how tiny perturbations affect the geometry of a traversable wormhole. The mathematical framework presented below helps us analyze the changes in the geometry due to a tiny perturbation in the radius of the throat δr_0 . The change in the geometry is expressed by δr_0 , $\delta b(r_0)$ and $\delta b(r_0 + \delta r_0)$. Here, δr represents the perturbations along the radial coordinate, while δr_0 denotes perturbation at the throat.

The throat of the wormhole is defined by the condition [1]: $b(r_0) = r_0$

Let us assume tiny perturbations affecting the geometry of the wormhole : δr_0 , $\delta b(r_0)$.

Let us denote the new shape function, the new radius at the throat, and the new shape function shifted from the throat as $b^n(r_0)$, r_0^n and $b^n(r_0^n)$.

Effects of perturbations:

$$b^n(r_0) = b(r_0) + \delta b(r_0) \quad (7.1)$$

$$r_0^n = r_0 + \delta r_0 \quad (7.2)$$

Since $b(r_0) = r_0$, the perturbed throat condition gives

$$b^n(r_0^n) = r_0^n \quad (7.3)$$

Substituting (7.1) and (7.2) into (7.3),

$$b(r_0 + \delta r_0) + \delta b(r_0 + \delta r_0) = r_0 + \delta r_0 \quad (7.4)$$

Using first-order Taylor expansion,

$$b(r_0 + \delta r_0) = b(r_0) + b'(r_0) \delta r_0 \quad (7.5)$$

$$\delta b(r_0 + \delta r_0) = \delta b(r_0) + \delta b'(r_0) \delta r_0$$

Since $\delta b'(r_0)$ and δr_0 are both small, their product is second order and may be neglected. Hence,

$$\delta b(r_0 + \delta r_0) \approx \delta b(r_0) \quad (7.6)$$

Substituting (7.5) and (7.6) into (7.4),

$$b(r_0) + b'(r_0)\delta r_0 + \delta b(r_0) = r_0 + \delta r_0$$

Using $b(r_0) = r_0$,

$$\begin{aligned} b'(r_0)\delta r_0 + \delta b(r_0) &= \delta r_0 \\ \delta r_0 [b'(r_0) - 1] &= -\delta b(r_0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{\therefore \delta r_0 = \frac{\delta b(r_0)}{1 - b'(r_0)}} \quad (7)$$

This relation holds within the linear perturbative regime [13] and assumes that higher-order terms are negligible.

We may now analyze the behavior of this result at two extreme values of $b'(r_0)$ between 0 and 1.

Case I: When $b'(r_0) \rightarrow 1^-$
Denominator = $1 - b'(r_0) \Rightarrow 1 - 1 = 0$

$$\delta r_0 = \frac{\delta b(r_0)}{0}$$

This results in a huge value, which indicates that a tiny perturbation can cause a huge shift in the throat radius, making the wormhole fragile and highly sensitive to perturbations.

Case II: When $b'(r_0) \rightarrow 0^+$
Denominator = $1 - b'(r_0) \Rightarrow 1 - 0 = 1$

$$\delta r_0 = \delta b(r_0)$$

This result shows that the perturbation creates only a small change in the geometry. This small change suggests reduced sensitivity to perturbations.

Case III: Let $b'(r_0) = 1 - \epsilon$, where ϵ is a very small value.

Denominator = $1 - b'(r_0) \Rightarrow 1 - (1 - \epsilon) = \epsilon$

$$\delta r_0 = \frac{\delta b(r_0)}{\epsilon}$$

This result shows that if ϵ is a very small value, then the shift in the radius of the throat δr_0 may be huge. Thus; it may make the geometry of the wormhole fragile and strongly sensitive to disturbances.

The results in this subsection are currently based on geometric manipulation. In the next subsection, we shall represent the result of δr_0 in terms of changes in energy density due to perturbations, establishing a coupling between the geometry and energy density.

2. Interdependence among δr_0 , $\delta \rho$ and $\tau_r(r_0)$ demonstrating Geometry - Matter Coupling

In this subsection, we shall represent the dependence between the geometry of the wormhole changed due to perturbations and its impact on the consistently distributed exotic matter i.e., energy density. We shall analyze these changes with the help of the mathematical framework given below:

A relation between energy density and the shape function is obtained by inserting Einstein's Field Equations into the Morris-Thorne Metric [1]:

$$\rho(r) = \frac{b'(r)}{8\pi r^2} \quad (8)$$

Let us perturb the equation:

$$\rho + \delta \rho = \frac{b'(r+\delta r)}{8\pi(r+\delta r)^2}$$

Using a Taylor Expansion:

$$\rho + \delta \rho = \frac{b'(r) + b''(r)\delta r + \delta b'(r)}{8\pi(r^2 + 2r\delta r)}$$

Here, $\delta b'(r)$ is a perturbation in the radial derivative of the shape function. It indicates the localized changes induced in the geometric profile of the wormhole due to perturbations. While it is treated as an explicit perturbation term in the perturbative expansion, it is implicitly coupled to $\delta \rho$ and δr through Einstein's field equations.

$$\rho + \delta \rho = \frac{b'(r) + b''(r)\delta r + \delta b'(r)}{8\pi r^2 \left(1 + \frac{2\delta r}{r}\right)}$$

Using the property: $\frac{1}{1+x} \approx 1 - x$, $x \ll 1$

$$\rho + \delta \rho = \frac{b'(r) + b''(r)\delta r + \delta b'(r)}{8\pi r^2} \left(1 - \frac{2\delta r}{r}\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{8\pi r^2} [b'(r) + b''(r)\delta r + \delta b'(r)] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{8\pi r^2} \left(\frac{2b'(r)\delta r}{r}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{b'(r)}{8\pi r^2} + \frac{\delta b'(r) + b''(r)\delta r}{8\pi r^2} \\ &\quad - \frac{b'(r)}{8\pi r^2} \left(\frac{2\delta r}{r}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\delta \rho(r) = \frac{1}{8\pi r^2} [\delta b'(r) + b''(r)\delta r] - \rho \left(\frac{2\delta r}{r}\right) \quad (9)$$

Evaluating at $r = r_0$

$$\delta\rho(r_0) = \frac{1}{8\pi r_0^2} [\delta b'(r_0) + b''(r_0) \delta r_0] - \rho \left(\frac{2\delta r_0}{r_0} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\therefore \tau_r(r_0) = \frac{1}{8\pi r_0^2} \quad (\text{derived in section III.C.3})$$

The result may also be written as:

$$\delta\rho(r_0) = \tau_r(r_0) \cdot [\delta b'(r_0) + b''(r_0) \delta r_0] - \rho \left(\frac{2\delta r_0}{r_0} \right) \quad (11)$$

where $\tau_r(r_0)$ represents the radial tension at the throat of the wormhole i.e., $r = r_0$.

In the following result, the perturbation in energy density $\delta\rho$ near the throat on the left side of the equation depends on the perturbation in throat radius δr_0 , the shape function, and the radial tension (or negative radial pressure) $\tau_r(r_0)$ at the throat on the right side of the equation. Thus, it indicates that the change in geometry influences the perturbations in the stress-energy configuration.

Now, we will represent the perturbation in radius and the shape function in terms of a definite integral of the changes caused by the disturbances in the distribution of energy density.

From the previous result:

$$\delta\rho(r) = \frac{1}{8\pi r^2} [\delta b'(r) + b''(r) \delta r] - \rho \left(\frac{2\delta r}{r} \right)$$

This result can be rearranged as follows:

$$8\pi r^2 (\delta\rho + \frac{2\rho\delta r}{r}) - b''(r) \delta r = \delta b'(r)$$

Integrating both sides with respect to r :

$$\int \delta b'(r) dr = \int [8\pi r^2 (\delta\rho + \frac{2\rho\delta r}{r}) - b''(r) \delta r] dr$$

$$\delta b(r) = \int [8\pi (\delta\rho r^2 + 2\rho r \delta r) - b''(r) \delta r] dr$$

Evaluating at $r = r_0$

$$\delta b(r_0) = \int_{r_{ref.}}^{r_0} [8\pi (\delta\rho r^2 + 2\rho r \delta r) - b''(r) \delta r] dr$$

where $r_{ref.}$ is a reference radial coordinate.

Substituting this value of $\delta b(r_0)$ into the result of δr_0

$$\delta r_0 = \frac{\int_{r_{ref.}}^{r_0} [8\pi (\delta\rho r^2 + 2\rho r \delta r) - b''(r) \delta r] dr}{1 - b'(r_0)} \quad (12)$$

We can reduce this general integral by substituting ρ and $\delta\rho$. The integral reduces to an expression involving $\delta b'(r)$, yielding:

$$\delta r_0 = \frac{\int_{r_{ref.}}^{r_0} \delta b'(r) dr}{1 - b'(r_0)} \quad (13)$$

$$\therefore \delta r_0 = \frac{\delta b(r_0) - \delta b(r_{ref.})}{1 - b'(r_0)} \quad (14)$$

This relation holds consistent with equation (7) as we assume an asymptotically flat region in spacetime, where $r_{ref.} \rightarrow \infty \implies \delta b(\infty) = 0$.

The results (12) and (13) present the coupling of a perturbation in geometry (δr_0) and perturbations in energy density ($\delta\rho$). The equations also demonstrate that the change in the shape function is not entirely local at the throat i.e., $r = r_0$. Rather, those changes are the result of cumulative distribution of perturbations in the energy density across the radial coordinate.

They also describe that even if the throat region is locally controlled, disturbances elsewhere can still influence it. This depicts the mutual coupling between the two. Thus, the geometry of a traversable wormhole is quite sensitive to the perturbations in energy density occurring in a region between a reference radial coordinate and the throat radius.

We now analyze the changes in the stress-energy configuration induced by a perturbation for a specific choice of shape function. Hence, we choose the shape function $b(r) = r_0^2/r$ of a traversable wormhole, which satisfies the Morris-Thorne condition and requires exotic matter to sustain the throat.

$$\text{If } b(r) = \frac{r_0^2}{r}$$

$$b'(r) = \frac{-r_0^2}{r^2}, b'(r_0) = -1 \text{ and } b''(r) = 2\frac{r_0^2}{r^3}$$

$$\text{We know, } \rho(r) = \frac{b'(r)}{8\pi r^2}$$

$$\text{Substituting } b'(r) = \frac{-r_0^2}{r^2}$$

$$\rho(r) = \frac{-r_0^2}{8\pi r^4}$$

$$\text{Now, } \delta\rho(r) = \frac{1}{8\pi r^2} [\delta b'(r) + b''(r) \delta r] - \rho \left(\frac{2\delta r}{r} \right)$$

Substituting $\rho(r)$ and $b''(r)$

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\rho(r) &= \frac{1}{8\pi r^2} \left[\delta b'(r) + 2 \left(\frac{r_0^2 \delta r}{r^3} \right) \right] + 2 \left(\frac{r_0^2 \delta r}{8\pi r^5} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi r^2} \left[\delta b'(r) + 4 \left(\frac{r_0^2 \delta r}{r^3} \right) \right]\end{aligned}$$

Assuming that the region is asymptotically flat; thus, $r_{ref.} \rightarrow \infty$

$$\delta r_0 = \frac{\int_{\infty}^{r_0} \left[8\pi(\delta\rho r^2 + 2\rho r \delta r) - b''(r) \delta r \right] dr}{1 - b'(r_0)}$$

Substituting $b'(r_0) = -1$

$$\delta r_0 = 4\pi \int_{\infty}^{r_0} \left[\delta\rho r^2 + 2\rho r \delta r - \frac{b''(r) \delta r}{8\pi} \right] dr$$

Substituting $\delta\rho, \rho, b''(r)$

$$\begin{aligned}\delta r_0 &= 4\pi \int_{\infty}^{r_0} \left[\frac{1}{8\pi r^2} \left(\delta b'(r) + \frac{4 r_0^2 \delta r}{r^3} \right) r^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2 \left(\frac{-r_0^2}{8\pi r^4} \right) r \delta r \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 2 \left(\frac{r_0^2}{8\pi r^3} \delta r \right) \right] dr\end{aligned}$$

Reversing limits introduces the negative sign

$$\delta r_0 = - \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\delta b'(r)}{2} + \frac{2r_0^2 \delta r}{r^3} - \frac{r_0^2 \delta r}{r^3} - \frac{r_0^2 \delta r}{r^3} \right] dr$$

$$\therefore \delta r_0 = - \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\delta b'(r)}{2} \right] dr \quad (15)$$

$$\boxed{\therefore \delta r_0 = - \frac{1}{2} [\delta b(r)] \Big|_{r_0}^{\infty}} \quad (16)$$

Now we shall derive $\delta b(r)$ for a specific shape function of choice.

Assuming flat spacetime yields:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} b(r) = 0$$

Now let us perturb this limit:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} [b(r) + \delta b(r)] = 0$$

$$\therefore \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \delta b(r) = 0 \implies \delta b(\infty) = 0 \quad (17)$$

From (16) : $\delta r_0 = -\frac{1}{2} [\delta b(\infty) - \delta b(r_0)]$

Substituting (17) into this relation, we get:

$$\boxed{\therefore \delta r_0 = \frac{1}{2} \delta b(r_0)} \quad (18)$$

This relation demonstrates that a perturbation in the throat induces a disturbance in the geometry of the wormhole at the throat, $\delta r_0 \propto \delta b(r_0)$.

This result is an extension of the integral in equation (12), solved by assuming a specific wormhole shape function. While, the general integral demonstrates that the effects induced by the perturbation are non-local, for this specific shape function $b(r) = r_0^2/r$ the integral reduces to a boundary expression, effectively consolidating the non-local contributions into the value of the perturbation at the throat.

Although the final relation $\delta r_0 = \frac{1}{2} \delta b(r_0)$ does not explicitly contain any stress-energy term, the coupling of geometry and matter is not eliminated. The shape function itself is dependent on stress-energy distribution through Einstein's field equations [5]. Consequently, the perturbation in throat radius and its geometry remains implicitly sensitive to the stress-energy configuration.

In this result, the constant 1/2 acts as an attenuation, which essentially causes the contribution of the perturbation at the throat to be reduced. Although the general equation (12) for δr_0 shows that the amplification is governed by $(1 - b'(r))^{-1}$, for the specific shape function of choice, where $b'(r_0) = -1$, it reduces to a damping factor of $\frac{1}{2}$.

Now, we consider a parametric perturbation $r_0 \rightarrow r_0 + \delta r_0$, preserving the functional form of the shape function.

The shape function of choice: $b(r) = r_0^2/r$

Let us perturb this equation:

$$\begin{aligned}b(r) + \delta b(r) &= \frac{(r_0 + \delta r_0)^2}{r} \\ &= \frac{r_0^2 + 2r_0 \delta r_0}{r}\end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{\delta b(r) = \frac{2 r_0 \delta r_0}{r}} \quad (19)$$

This relation represents a parametric perturbation of the shape function induced by a variation in the throat radius $r_0 \rightarrow r_0 + \delta r_0$. It describes how a change in the

parametric perturbation affects the shape function across the radial coordinate. The inverse radial dependence $1/r$ indicates that the sensitivity of the geometry to the variations in r_0 decreases with the distance from the throat.

3. Variation Of Radial Tension Under Perturbations

Radial Pressure refers to the pressure exerted along the radial direction at the throat of the wormhole. It can be positive or negative, indicating compression or tension, respectively. In a traversable wormhole, the stress-energy configuration requires the presence of negative radial pressure; which is referred to as the radial tension $\tau_r(r_0)$.

As derived in [1], the radial tension is given by:

$$\tau_r(r) = \frac{1}{8\pi G} \left[\frac{b(r)}{r^3} - \frac{2\Phi'(r)}{r} \left(1 - \frac{b(r)}{r} \right) \right] \quad (20)$$

$c = 1$ [Geometrized units]

Here, $\tau_r(r)$ represents radial tension, G is the Universal Gravitational Constant, $b(r)$ is the shape function, and $\Phi(r)$ represents the redshift function.

Evaluating at $r = r_0$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_r(r_0) &= \frac{1}{8\pi G} \left[\frac{b(r_0)}{r_0^3} - \frac{2\Phi'(r_0)}{r_0} \left(1 - \frac{b(r_0)}{r_0} \right) \right] \\ \therefore b(r_0) &= r_0 \\ \tau_r(r_0) &= \frac{1}{8\pi r_0^2}, \quad G = 1 \text{ [Geometrized units]} \\ \therefore \tau_r(r_0) &\propto \frac{1}{r_0^2} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Let the perturbations change the radius of the throat i.e., r_0 such that :

New radius, say, $r_0^n = r_0 + \delta r_0$

The radial tension of the perturbed radius would be

$$\tau_r(r_0 + \delta r_0) = \frac{1}{8\pi(r_0 + \delta r_0)^2}$$

We know, $r_0 < r_0 + \delta r_0$,

$$\implies r_0^2 < (r_0 + \delta r_0)^2, \text{ assuming } \delta r_0 > 0$$

$$\boxed{\therefore \tau(r_0) > \tau(r_0^n)} \quad (22)$$

The result shows that the radial tension of new radius (or perturbed radius) is less than the radial tension of radius under normal conditions. Since radial tension at the throat depends inversely on the square of the throat radius, perturbations lead to variations in the radial tension. The changes caused by perturbations in the shape function, combined with those in the radial tension, suggest that the stress-energy configuration required to sustain the wormhole is sensitive to small disturbances.

D. Violation Of The Flare-Out Condition

The Flare-Out Condition is a geometric requirement that must be satisfied for the existence of a traversable wormhole [1, 4]. In this subsection, we shall analyze the change in the Flare-Out Condition if $b'(r_0) \geq 1$. The inequality representing this condition :

$$\implies \frac{b(r) - b'(r)r}{2[b(r)]^2} > 0 \quad (23)$$

Evaluating the Flare-Out Condition at the throat i.e., $r = r_0$

$$\frac{b(r_0) - b'(r_0)r_0}{2[b(r_0)]^2} > 0 \quad (24)$$

$b'(r_0) < 1$ is a popular result of the Flare-Out Condition. However, in this subsection, we shall analyze the changes in the Flare-Out Condition and their impact on the wormhole by violating this inequality.

Let's assume $b'(r_0) \geq 1$

We may also assume $b'(r_0) = 1 + \epsilon$, for $\epsilon \geq 0$

Substituting $b'(r_0) = 1 + \epsilon$ in equation (24):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{b(r_0) - (1+\epsilon)r_0}{2[b(r_0)]^2} \\ \therefore b(r_0) &= r_0 \\ \implies \frac{r_0 - (1+\epsilon)r_0}{2[r_0]^2} &= \frac{r_0[1-1-\epsilon]}{2r_0^2} = \frac{-\epsilon}{2r_0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \epsilon \geq 0$$

$$\boxed{\frac{-\epsilon}{2r_0} > 0} \quad (25)$$

The substitution yield $\frac{-\epsilon}{2r_0} > 0$. Since $\epsilon \geq 0$, $r_0 > 0$, the left hand side of the inequality becomes non-positive (negative). Hence, the result does not satisfy the flare-out condition, as it is a mathematical contradiction.

$\therefore \epsilon \geq 0 \implies$ this expression $\frac{-\epsilon}{2r_0}$, representing the flare-out condition, gives a negative value when $\epsilon > 0$. However, if $\epsilon = 0$, the resultant inequality is $0 > 0$, which is mathematically inconsistent.

This result violates the flare-out condition, since the quantity appearing in the inequality is required to be strictly positive. The flare-out condition constitutes a necessary geometric criterion for the existence of a traversable wormhole. The expression obtained above therefore represents a direct violation of this condition in the regime $b'(r_0) \geq 1$.

Therefore, for all values of $b'(r_0)$ that are greater than or equal to 1, this configuration does not satisfy the flare-out condition required for a traversable wormhole.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the entire Section III, we analyzed whether a traversable wormhole can sustain under the most optimistic conditions. We made four generous assumptions in this section, which include the existence and access to exotic matter, the redshift function being finite everywhere in the geometry of the wormhole, the geometry being static as well as symmetric, and assuming that the geometry satisfies the flare-out condition.

In the subsections, we analyzed the sustenance of the wormhole by violating the null energy condition, using perturbation theory in the first-order correction, and by violating the flare-out condition. We analyzed the results and reached conclusions that indicate that even under maximal optimistic assumptions, the geometry of the wormhole is highly sensitive to tiny changes in energy density, radial pressure, shape function, or the throat radius of the wormhole. However, *Case II* of section III.C.1 showcases reduced sensitivity to those changes.

The results obtained in this paper indicate that the wormhole geometry is sensitive to the changes induced by the perturbations. The relation of δr_0 in terms of a definite integral reveals a coupling between geometry and the stress-energy configuration, indicating that the perturbations are not entirely local at the throat. Moreover, sustaining a wormhole requires a stress-energy configuration in which the radial tension exceeds the energy density. In Section III.C.3, we observed that the radial tension at the throat reduces due to perturbations in the geometry.

Maintaining such a configuration may be physically difficult under extreme stress-energy conditions. Therefore, even under the most optimistic assumptions, the wormhole geometry appears to be extremely difficult.

A. Summary Of The Key Results

- $\tau_r(r_0) > \rho(r_0)$

This inequality in section III.B between radial tension and energy density indicates that sustaining the wormhole geometry requires radial tension to exceed the energy density at the throat.

- $\delta r_0 = \frac{\delta b(r_0)}{1-b'(r_0)}$

This result in section III.C.1 shows that perturbations in the shape function induce changes in the throat radius. It becomes highly sensitive with

$b'(r_0) \rightarrow 1$. This indicates that the geometry remains highly sensitive in general, with specific regimes exhibiting reduced sensitivity as in *Case II*. We have analyzed the behavior of the perturbed throat radius δr_0 at different values of $b'(r_0)$.

- $\delta \rho(r_0) = \tau_r(r_0) [\delta b'(r_0) + b''(r_0) \delta r_0] - \rho\left(\frac{2\delta r_0}{r_0}\right)$

This equation establishes the coupling among energy density, radial tension, and the geometry of the wormhole. It highlights that perturbations in the geometry are directly linked to the perturbations in the stress-energy distribution.

- $\delta r_0 = \frac{\int_{r_{ref.}}^{r_0} [8\pi(\delta \rho r^2 + 2\rho r \delta r) - b''(r) \delta r] dr}{1-b'(r_0)}$

The result reveals that a perturbation at the throat and the cumulative distribution of energy density perturbations between a reference radial coordinate ($r_{ref.}$) and the throat (r_0) are coupled and interdependent. This result indicates that the perturbations in the wormhole geometry are induced by non-local effects rather than being purely localized at one specific point.

- $\delta r_0 = \frac{1}{2} \delta b(r_0)$

This relation is a result obtained by establishing a matter-geometry coupling and assuming a specific shape function of choice $b(r) = r_0^2/r$ and an asymptotically flat region. It indicates that a perturbation in the radius can induce the throat to either expand or contract, depending on the nature of the perturbation. $\delta b(r)$ represents the perturbation in the shape function, indicating the changes induced in the geometric profile of the wormhole. It also induces shifts in the radius of the throat.

- $\tau(r_0) > \tau(r_0^n)$ (where $r_0^n = r_0 + \delta r_0$)

This inequality in section III.C.3 highlights that a perturbation in the throat radius leads to a reduction in the radial tension as $\tau_r(r_0) \propto \frac{1}{r_0^2}$, further contributing to the sensitivity of the stress-energy configuration.

- $\frac{-\epsilon}{2r_0} > 0$

The inequality shows the violation of the flare-out condition. We get this result when we substitute $b'(r_0) \geq 1$. This configuration does not satisfy the flare-out condition required for a traversable wormhole. This result confirms that wormhole geometry with $b'(r_0) \geq 1$ violates the flare-out condition and does not lead to the formation of a traversable wormhole.

B. Physical Implications

Almost all of the results in Section III indicate that the response of the wormhole geometry is highly sensitive to perturbations. It implies that wormholes respond to perturbations induced in their geometry. In the earlier sections, we observed that the responses in the wormhole geometry are directly dependent on the shape function $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r})$, its related derivatives such as $\mathbf{b}'(\mathbf{r}_0)$, and the stress-energy configuration. The term $\mathbf{b}'(\mathbf{r}_0)$ refers to the rate of change in the shape function at the throat. We have analyzed the key role of this term in Subsection III.C.1 and Subsection III.D. When $\mathbf{b}'(\mathbf{r}_0) \rightarrow \mathbf{1}^-$, the perturbation induces the throat radius to diverge in response rather than exhibiting stabilizing behavior.

A significant relation between the wormhole geometry and the stress-energy distribution, which establishes a coupling between matter and geometry, is presented in Subsection III.C.2 in the form of a general definite integral and is subsequently solved for a specific shape function of choice $\delta\mathbf{r}_0 = \frac{1}{2}\delta\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r}_0)$. The definite integral demonstrates the non-local behavior of the changes in the stress-energy configuration induced by perturbations in the throat radius. The perturbations in the throat radius and the perturbations in the stress-energy configuration are interdependent as well as coupled. This indicates that the perturbations in the throat are not only localized there but also impact the cumulative distribution of matter along the radial coordinate. Consequently, the wormhole geometry is influenced by non-local effects, where disturbances in one region can influence the entire geometry. Therefore, it can be concluded that the stability of the wormhole is not local at the throat or at any specific point.

Under the optimistic assumptions, including the availability of exotic matter through the violation of the null energy condition in Section III.A, we analyzed whether a traversable wormhole would be sustainable. However, our further analysis indicates that exotic matter alone is insufficient to ensure the stability of wormholes.

Our results show that sustaining a traversable wormhole requires precise coordination of *geometry-matter* coupling. Thus, sustaining a traversable wormhole requires a precise and consistent configuration of both geometry and stress-energy. In conclusion, sustaining such a configuration requires fine-tuned coordination between geometry and stress-energy, as small perturbations can induce amplified responses near the throat.

C. Limitations and Future Scope

The analysis in this paper is restricted to first-order perturbation theory, providing only an approximation of the results. We assumed the geometry of the wormhole to be static and symmetric for analytical tractability. Thus, we

have not evaluated the wormhole geometry dynamically. Allowing the violation of the Null Energy Condition for the existence of exotic matter was another optimistic assumption made in the paper. However, in reality, while quantum effects such as the Casimir Effect indicate the presence of localized negative energy density, no evidence has been discovered that showcases the existence of large-scale exotic matter capable of sustaining a macroscopic wormhole. The result obtained in Section III.C.2 represents the perturbation in the throat radius $\delta\mathbf{r}_0$ in terms of the energy density; however, this result is expressed in the form of a definite integral and is not explicitly evaluated. Though we have solved the integral by substituting a specific shape function of choice $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{r}_0^2/\mathbf{r}$, this serves as a concrete realization of the general framework, demonstrating how the integral can be evaluated for $\delta\mathbf{r}_0$ under specific geometric conditions.

Future work may involve a more detailed dynamical analysis of the wormhole using the Kerr-like wormhole geometry. The first-order perturbation analysis provided an approximation, and thus, higher-order perturbation methods are required for more accurate results [13]. Moreover, further constraints, such as quantum backreaction and other quantum constraints, have to be assessed for a better analysis of sustaining a traversable wormhole. Nevertheless, in the relation between the perturbation in the throat radius and stress-energy distribution, the general framework involving a definite integral has to be evaluated to obtain a more accurate relation.

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